

Education as Key to Empower, Progress and Brighter Future for Women

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ABSTRACT

Undoubtedly education can bring revolution by producing competent human potential, contributing to establish an equitable and just society and ensuring national development. But it's possible only when we will change ourselves with the help of same education which we have acquired. When education will have full effect on our heart in respect the eyes of heart will be enlightened fully with the indelible influence of education and will surely lead us to the right way by maintaining and doing justice with ourselves first then certainly justice will be done by us with everyone else. Undoubtedly, education is a key for enhancing the status, name and fame of women. It is worth mentioning that education is the basic fundamental and prerequisite for brightening the future life of women, as it brings Transparency, accountability, commitment, efficiency and better socio-economic betterment for their utmost survival and sustenance. The prosperity of a country is closely linked to its educational landscape. Education is a fundamental requirement for empowerment, as its primary goal is to awaken awareness and consciousness. In the pursuit of empowerment, education acts as a powerful tool, offering exposure to new ideas, ways of thinking, and fostering a demand for change. Without an education

that aligns with both existing knowledge and real-world needs, women face significant barriers to accessing formal sector jobs, advancing in their careers, participating in decision-making processes at all levels, or gaining political representation and influence. It is important to note that educated women are more effective in improving their own well-being and the welfare of their families. Hence education is the most precious wealth blessed to all of us and it is mandatory that we must respect our education. We must use it for the purpose for which it has been blessed to all of us. We must introspect ourselves, our efficiency, our knowledge, our capacities and must always try to enhance all these factors equal.

Introduction:

Education is incredibly an amazing key tool for uplifting women, as it can help them improve their lives and the lives of their families. Possessing this enormous tendency it's also helpful for women by gaining the knowledge, skills and confidence to make informed decisions about their lives, including their education, career and health. Not only this, it can also assist women to expand their employment opportunities and increase their earning potential. Acting as a powerful tool, it shines as a light that guides them out of darkness to light. Despite empowers women with the much required skills, knowledge and tools to make optimistic decisions, secure their status, name, fame, position and most of all achieving the better standard of life and granting them fundamental rights, policies, amendments for living a free, fair and congenial life and maintaining their overall and complete wellbeing. In today's context, empowerment is seen as a means to create a social environment where crucial decisions can be made, and choices can be taken to drive social transformation. The famous quote that "If you educate a man you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family. Women empowered means mother India empowered " (Bhat, 2015; Tamil selvi, 2018). With realization and awareness, the women are able to think different about their needs and requirements. Self- expression and spirit has to be utilized to maintain awareness and familiarity related to empowerment and Upliftment. It is this inner strength that enables women to take proactive steps to secure the best possible outcomes for their survival and success.

The role of the social is incredibly important as it dedicates the justice, solidarity, compassion and cooperation, which are primarily vital for building and creating emphatic stance on all levels which can yield a constructive environment for women to prosper and enjoy a happy life. The study has proven that education possesses an enormous power to impart and transfer knowledge in preparing individuals Wani et al (2022), who can greatly contribute for this noblest cause of women empowerment and Upliftment. Education serves as a pivotal milestone in women's empowerment. It plays a crucial role in promoting equality, while also improving their status within the family, society, and political-economic spheres. Moreover, it is essential to recognize that empowerment involves empowering individuals to think critically, take independent action, and assume control over their own lives (Bhat, 2015; Kaur, 2018). A genuine commitment to empowerment requires structures that institutionalize respect for diversity, protect an individual's freedom, and provide the necessary resources to enable personal self-realization (Witte, 2019). Women's empowerment, based on the understanding that women's social positions differ from men's and that these differences are rooted in unequal power dynamics, Women's empowerment is the process of enhancing their ability to make important life decisions and granting them access to opportunities that allow them to reach their full potential. As an economic, political, and socio-cultural process, it challenges the system of gender-based stratification that has historically subordinated and marginalized women, aiming to improve their quality of life (Chant, 2018). Thus, the concept of women's empowerment encompasses three essential elements: power, autonomy, and subjectivity. First, three forms of power enhance women's ability to make strategic choices: "*Power with*," "*Power to*," and "*Power within*." "*Power with*" refers to collective or group-based Collaboration and relationships are defined by mutual support, respect, solidarity, influence, empowerment, and joint decision-making. The concept of "power with" fosters the creation of connections and bridges within groups or across differences, and can lead to collective action."Power to" refers to the ability to create something new, make a difference, or achieve goals. It's based on the idea that everyone has the potential to shape their life and world. It is refers to the potential of power to be productive or generative, and the new possibilities that can be created without domination. In simpler terms, "Power to" refers to the ability to learn, retain knowledge, and understand the significance of one's actions. In legal terms, it means the capacity to comprehend facts and the consequences of one's behavior, as well as the ability to act or accomplish tasks. Everyone has the power to improve themselves. This type of power is often associated with external symbols of authority, such as a title, uniform, or prominent position.

In essence, power can manifest in both upward and downward directions. "Power within," on the other hand, is the internal strength that relates to a person's self-worth, self-awareness, and the ability to appreciate and respect differences in others. It also includes the capacity for imagination, hope, and the belief that one can make a positive impact. "Power within" is often linked with other forms of power, such as "*Power with*," which fosters collaboration and collective action within teams. Additionally, "Power to" emphasizes the potential of every individual to shape their own life and environment. In contrast, "*Power over*" refers to power built on force, coercion, and domination, where control is exerted over others. Thus, the concept of "power within" is also explored in the book, *The Power Within*, which offers practical techniques and insights to help women to discover their own power. Hence, both the above three key-elements are profoundly important for contributing the women in the following ways like the ability to act or to do something, the possession of control, authority, or influence over others, physical might, mental strength, the rate at which the work is done or energy is given off or transferred. Thus, women's empowerment is a process that enables women to make choices and take control of their lives.

Methodology

This study adopted review based approach for exploring "Education as Key to Empower, Progress, and a Brighter Future for Women" involves secondary data understand the lived perceptions of women. Participants will include women from diverse socio-economic backgrounds, regions, and educational levels. The data collection focused on how education influences their personal empowerment, economic mobility, and social progress. Themes such as access to education, barriers faced, and transformative outcomes will be explored. Content analysis will be used to identify common patterns, while thematic coding will allow for the examination of recurring narratives around education as a tool for women's empowerment. The findings will offer insights into the critical role of education in shaping a brighter, more equitable future for women. The investigator has mainly used secondary data such as pre-reviewed articles, books, newspapers and other scholarly resources that has been extracted from different data bases like Google Scholar, ERIC, Academic , JSTOR, PubMed.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the role of education in enhancing women's empowerment by providing access to opportunities for personal, economic, and social advancement.

2. To explore how education contributes to shaping a brighter future for women by fostering skills, self-confidence, and decision-making power, leading to greater societal progress.

Major results of study

Education as Empowerment Tool

Our country is experiencing dynamic growth in various sectors, with a booming economy, cutting-edge technology, and improved infrastructure becoming sources of national pride. While there have been advancements across many fields, the discrimination against the girl child continues to persist. As M. Phule aptly stated, "Education is that which distinguishes between good and evil." If we reflect on this definition, we can conclude that education is at the heart of all progress and reform in history. Education brings about positive change in all aspects of life, such as mental development, perspective, and attitude. Educated women contribute to the education of their daughters as well. Additionally, educated women play a crucial role in reducing infant mortality rates and controlling population growth. Empowering women has thus become a central topic of global discussion and focus. Education serves as a powerful tool for empowerment by providing individuals, particularly women, with the knowledge, skills, and confidence to overcome societal barriers. It enables them to make informed decisions, access better opportunities, and contribute meaningfully to their communities. Women should have equal rights with men in all areas, including education, employment, nutrition, inheritance, marriage, and politics, among others. However, it is undeniable that their long struggle for fundamental rights, such as equality, has led to the creation of numerous women's committees, associations, organizations, NGOs, and the launch of various movements. Women shapes the destiny of the society, such is the tragic irony that this beautiful creation of Almighty Allah is facing such gravest concerns in this fast paced global world. Empowerment enables individuals to realize their full potential, enhance their political and social involvement, and develop confidence in their own abilities and strengths. Ensuring all the above requirements of women shall solidify her to enhance her status, position, role and standard of life in the present day world and bring a positive change among them, and shall enable to respond to their hardships.

Significance of women education:

The importance of women's education cannot be emphasized enough, as it has a profound impact on individuals, families, and society as a whole. Educating women serves as a powerful means of empowerment, providing them with the skills and knowledge to improve their own lives while making valuable contributions to the progress of their communities and nations. Research shows that educated women are more likely to join the workforce, earn higher incomes, and attain greater financial independence (World Bank, 2018). This not only raises the standard of living for women but also fosters broader economic growth.

Moreover, women's education has a profound impact on future generations. Educated mothers prioritize their children's education, leading to improved literacy and social mobility. Studies show that children of educated women are healthier, experience lower mortality rates, and have better opportunities for education (UNICEF, 2019). The benefits also extend to social and political realms. Educated women participate in decision-making, in household matters and in broader societal structures, leading to more gender-equitable policies and practices. As the United Nations (2020) reports, empowering women through education is one of the most effective strategies to achieve sustainable development and reduce inequality worldwide.

UNICEF

It is important to pen down that investing in women education is one of the most transformative developmental strategies, the need of the time is prioritize efforts that enables all the Encourages female students to finish secondary education and skill based knowledge are necessary for their future lives. vocation cum occupation. History stands witness to the fact that women Education plays a key role in development by lowering fertility rates and improving the health of women and children. It enables individuals to earn higher incomes, engage in decisions that impact their lives, and create better life prospects. The best use of education is that which trains an educated person as much as possible and creates in him the ability to avoid all kinds of harm to himself. If education will have an effect on the heart along with the mind of a person, then the eyes of a person's heart will definitely be enlightened and with the light of the eyes of the heart, a person will always try to do justice to himself and then to all others. When an educated person will have the ability to avoid all kinds of harm and the eyes of his heart will be enlightened, he will surely do justice to himself and certainly with all others. It means in order to do full justice to themselves all the teachers must impart quality education to the children with full dedication, sincerity and honesty, all that is needed is to think and understand the truth and real benefit

of education blessed and graced to all the members of the teaching community. When every member will understand such power and purpose of education and will make its proper use as mentioned above the change will be certainly possible in the scenario of imparting quality education.

Education

Since education is the most precious wealthy blessed to all of us and it is mandatory that we must respect our education. Now full respect of Education would be that :we must use it for the purpose for which it has been blessed to all of us. we must introspect ourselves, our efficiency, our knowledge, our capacities, our capabilities and must always try to enhance all these factors equal or rather more than most genius colleagues so that we can give maximum benefit to our community cum society by enhancing the standard of women by imparting quality education to them and making full use of their inner potential and talent for their Upliftment cum empowerment.

Role of education in raising the social status and dignity of a women:

Education empowers women by equipping them with the knowledge and skills needed to challenge social stereotypes and assert their rights, thereby enhancing their social status. As women gain education, they become more confident, independent, and capable of contributing to society, which elevates their dignity and fosters respect (Jha, 2014). It is a powerful tool that allows women to expand their perspectives, enhance their understanding, and contribute to the development of families, communities, and the nation as a whole, fostering excellence and competitiveness. Education plays an essential role in improving the quality of life for women (Yousuf, 2019).

The key factors contributing to the disadvantaged position of women are their lack of awareness, powerlessness, and vulnerability (Shakuntala, 2005; Ojha, 2016). Education plays a crucial role in empowering women by informing them of their rights and providing them with the knowledge and tools to challenge economic and social discrimination (Nabi et al., 2024). Education plays a pivotal role in elevating women's social status and dignity by providing them with the knowledge, skills, and confidence to challenge societal norms. It empowers women to pursue careers, make informed decisions, and actively participate in social, political, and economic spheres, fostering respect and equality in society. (Bhat, 2015: Kour, 2018). Education can help raising the social dignity of women in many ways, including empowerment, Education can assist women gain the knowledge, skills and confidence to pursue their aspirations and assert their rights, Economic Independence Education can

help women secure better jobs, earn higher incomes Wani et al. (2022) and reduce their vulnerability to poverty, Challenging gender inequality. Education promoting social change. Education can help women become agents of change within their communities, promoting gender equality and social justice. Health and well-being. Education can help women improve their health outcomes by increasing their knowledge of nutrition, reproductive health, and disease prevention. UNESCO, considers education to be fundamental human right and a key driver of sustainable development and gender equality.

Empowerment as a milestone for uplifting women in this fast paced global world:

Empowerment is a crucial milestone for uplifting women in today's fast-paced global world. It enables women to take control of their lives, make independent decisions, and contribute meaningfully to society. In an era driven by technology, innovation, and rapid economic growth, empowerment ensures women have equal opportunities in education, the workforce, and leadership roles. It allows them to break free from traditional constraints, challenge societal norms, and achieve financial independence. Ultimately, empowerment is not just about individual success; it fosters collective growth, creating a more inclusive and balanced world for future generations. It is also regarded as the greatest tool by which we can boost women's standard through literacy, education, training and awareness creation, besides this it's elegance can be understood with the following important points; Sense of self-worth: Women should have a strong sense of self-worth.

CONCLUSION

Education is a powerful tool for empowering women, fostering progress, and creating a brighter future. By providing women with access to quality education, societies can break the cycle of poverty, reduce gender inequality, and unlock the full potential of half the population. Education equips women with the knowledge, skills, and confidence to participate in the workforce, make informed decisions, and contribute to their communities. It also promotes personal growth and self-reliance, leading to improved health, economic stability, and social mobility. As women rise through the educational ranks, they become catalysts for change, uplifting entire generations. Therefore, investing in women's education is not only a moral imperative but a practical strategy for sustainable development and social advancement, benefitting both women and society as a whole.

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